

THE ROLE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN ENSURING THE ECONOMIC SECURITY OF THE COUNTRY

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Abstract: *The article analyzes the role of entrepreneurship in ensuring the country's economic security. The place of entrepreneurship in the development of the socio-economic system of the state is considered. The role of entrepreneurship in the economic security of the country is shown and the positive dynamics of small business development is studied.*

Key words: *economic security, business, entrepreneurship, economic security of the state, principles of economic security, socio-economic system, sustainability, national economy.*

Economic security is one of the most important components of the country's national security. Therefore its provision is one of the most important national priorities.

Economic security is a fairly broad concept based on the study of such concepts as a developed socio-economic system that ensures the stability of the national economy and external, external influences that affect economic security.

One of the important directions in ensuring the sustainable development of the country is the development of small and private businesses in Uzbekistan.

From the first days of independence, Uzbekistan has paid great attention to the development of the legal framework, the organization of financial support, the protection of the rights of entrepreneurs, the training and retraining of personnel, the development of market infrastructure serving small businesses. Today, small business is an important element of the modern socio-economic system, without which the economy and society as a whole cannot exist and develop normally.

The advantages of small business in solving the problems of substituting imported goods are the active development of new types of goods, improving the quality of goods, works and services, small size in terms of key performance indicators, flexibility to changing market conditions and mobility compared to large enterprises.

In Uzbekistan small business continues to show growth rates. As of 2021, the share of small business in GDP was 54.9%. (1)

For comparison, the share of small and medium-sized businesses in the GDP of the industrial developed countries is around 50-60%: in Poland - 51%, Germany - 53%, Finland - 60%, the Netherlands - 63%.

One of the main indicators that showing the development of the business environment in the country in the world is the World Bank's report "Doing Business". The Report is the most authoritative, recognized and most cited study that evaluates the ease of doing business in various countries of the world according to special indicators. The position of a country in this ranking not only reflects the favorable business environment, but is also an important criterion for making investment decisions in the international business community.

Decree № PP4160 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as of May 2nd 2019 "On additional measures to improve the rating of the Republic Uzbekistan in the annual report of the World Bank and the International Finance Corporation "Doing Business" (2) set a target for the current year of reaching 20th place in the world. Also Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan №DP-6003 "On improving positions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in International rating and indices, as well as implementation in Government bodies and organizations of new mechanisms of working with them on systematic manner" (3).

The country creates all the necessary conditions for business development. The time and procedure for registering a small business was reduced, and bureaucratic obstacles were eliminated. Financial support is provided to small businesses, which is provided through the issuance of preferential bank loans; the guarantee of the State Fund for the Support and Development of Entrepreneurship to business entities in obtaining a loan; submission by the State Fund of compensation for interest expenses on loans from commercial banks.

The Commissioner for the Protection of the Rights and Legitimate Interests of Business Entities is responsible for protecting the interests of business. Unscheduled inspections of the activities of small businesses have been canceled in Uzbekistan, business entities are released from all types of liability that have committed financial and economic offenses for the first time.

The role of small business in ensuring the economic security of the state is great. The state, by developing entrepreneurship, makes it possible to more fully meet the needs of the population in goods and services, and also forms the local infrastructure. With the development of small business, a middle class appears, interested in the stability of the economy. The activity of small business is a source of tax revenues and participates in the formation of budgets at all levels. Entrepreneurship has a positive effect on the employment of the working population.

Large investments are not required to create small and medium-sized businesses. But, nevertheless, the development of small business affects the creation of a competitive environment. Small businesses are easier to manage and can innovate faster. Also small business is highly mobile and efficient, responding more flexibly to consumer demand, thanks to which it affects the smoothing of economic fluctuations.

In a market economy, the great role of entrepreneurship is emphasized. At this stage of development, small businesses are becoming more diverse, dynamic and reflect the needs of individual consumer groups, moving towards flexible and individualized production focused on certain market segments. The stable position of small business in the economy and its active participation in market competition causes a stronger opposition, which it exerts on the monopolization of the market.

Small business is most actively involved in the innovation process, as it has the ability to perceive and develop technical and technological innovations. During periods of economic downturn, small business has a stabilizing effect on the economic and social spheres. However, entrepreneurship is also vulnerable and needs help from the state. Entrepreneurship is involved in maintaining the dynamic socio-economic development of the country and ensures the stability and competitiveness of the national economy. All this is an integral part of ensuring the economic security of the state.

In order to create a favorable external environment for small and medium-sized businesses, the state is faced with the task of creating and thinking over a strategic state policy. The state should comprehensively help the development of small business and participate in its formation.

In a market environment, enterprises of various forms of ownership are at risk.

The main problems in the field of small business and private entrepreneurship are still considered to be the lack of own and borrowed funds, as a result of which small enterprises are not able to purchase modern and high-tech equipment,

problems and difficulties in obtaining land plots for business activities, problems in connection to engineering and communication networks.

It should also be noted that there is insufficient liquid collateral for a bank loan at the start of an entrepreneur's activity, which reduces the possibility of obtaining a loan. There are also difficulties in obtaining long-term loans that stimulate the formation and development of small innovative industrial enterprises.

There are no effective mechanisms for promoting small business products to regional and world markets, as well as the complexity of competition in the foreign market in certain sectors of the economy and the problems of entering foreign markets.

Among the problems it should be noted the lack of development of information systems, marketing, management and logistics services; insurance companies, audit firms, trading houses, consulting offices, business centers, business incubators; sales markets, as well as markets for raw materials and materials; low equipment of small enterprises with modern technological equipment that ensures the release of competitive products.

There is a weak training of specialists of a professional qualification level employed in small business.

At the same time, there are unresolved problems in the banking sector, many entrepreneurs point to high lending rates and commissions on bank operations, in particular, an additional fee is charged for consideration of submitted documents by the credit commission.

In addition, when obtaining a loan, entrepreneurs need to cover the costs of insurance and collateral valuation, notarization of loan documents, etc.

Along with this, banks set subscription fees and other commission fees for converting funds, opening a letter of credit, transferring converted funds to the account of foreign partner banks and other services, which is a significant financial burden for entrepreneurs who apply to commercial banks for financial support.

To prevent this situation, it is proposed to resume the activities of credit unions and microcredit organizations, which could become real competitors for commercial banks, which would reduce the rates.

Also, it is necessary that commercial banks recognize the valuation of collateral carried out by independent valuation organizations. Currently, the appraisal organization is indicated by the bank itself, and the value of the appraised collateral may be underestimated.

Proposed measures to stimulate the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship:

1. Subsequent easing of interest rates on loans, which will allow small businesses to reduce costs and ensure financial stability, because in world practice, the lower the loan rate, the more stimulated production growth and consumer demand;
2. Organize training of personnel with entrepreneurial skills, which is a catalyst for the development of small businesses and individual entrepreneurship for self-employment through the introduction of vocational education.
3. Continuing and strengthening the development of cooperation ties between large enterprises and small businesses, as well as holding cooperation fairs;
4. Cardinal simplification of the processes of coordinating land issues, registering buildings when transferred to the use or ownership of entrepreneurs;
5. Development and implementation of criteria for evaluating the activities of state authorities and local authorities for the development of entrepreneurship and the business environment as a whole;
6. Development of public-private partnership aimed at reducing business and investment risks in the areas of research and development, dissemination of new technologies;
7. Introduction of a mechanism for the transfer of shares of state-owned enterprises to the management of its employees who have been working in them for more than five years, which could give an additional incentive to these employees to think like an entrepreneur and work on the development of the enterprise.
8. Additional development of the mechanism and scientific substantiation of a set of measures of state support for a high level of economic security of small business is necessary.

The main functions of the state in relation to various forms of entrepreneurial activity are the regulatory and stimulating functions. The lack of mechanisms between business and the state for full-fledged bilateral work leads to a slowdown in the development of socio-economic processes. Thus, the mechanisms and forms of interaction between the state and business have a great influence on the behavior of enterprises and the incentives that govern their owners.

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